

PRONOMINAL PROCESSES IN ENGLISH AND IULEHA LANGUAGES: A CONTRASTIVE APPRAISAL

Prof. (Mrs.) B.O. Anyanwu
&
Mr. P.O Attashie
Department of English,
Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma,
Edo State – Nigeria.

Abstract

Language plays a vital role in human life. In a multilingual setting such as Nigeria, indigenous languages are endangered and suffer inadequate research to enhance their structure. Hence, the need for contrastive investigation of English and Iuleha in the field of linguistics has come to be of interest, not only to the historical linguist, but also to the sociolinguists who are interested in showing that language is not ‘homogenous’ but subject to change under different setting. The extent to which a people's language is developed and influenced, reflects on the people's cultures and behaviour, while its extinction affects the perception of the people. It is on this premise that this paper attempts a Contrastive Analysis of Pronominal Formation Processes in English and Iuleha Languages. The study adopts M.A.K. Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar Model as its theoretical Framework. The “Systemic Grammar” views language as a network of systems, or interrelated set of options for making meaning. This paper reveals that there are significant cross linguistic distinctions between English and Iuleha plural pronominal in the third person. Specifically, Iuleha plural pronominal make no gender distinction as English does. For instance, both he/she are unmarked for gender as in *nyòin* singular and *nyáin* plural (he/she/ Them), irrespective of the gender. Both the second person *they* and the third person *she* are realized in Iuleha by the voiced alveolar nasal sound /n/ as in (*nyòin/nyáin*). This paper safely concludes that tone plays a crucial role in Iuleha plural pronominal formation and there are differences and similarity in both languages.

Keyword: *Contrastive Analysis, Pronominal, Iuleha and English Language Learning.*

Introduction

The basic purpose of language is communication and language is as old as man. It is important to note, therefore, that language is inevitable because, it is the means through which humans communicate, interact, and exchange ideas into reality or pass information. With respect to English, which is used in Britain and the USA as the Mother Tongue (MT) on one the hand, and as a second language (L2) in other parts of the world, new words keep entering the lexicons of the language regularly. This point accounts for Wayne's view that “language is the major feature that distinguishes humans as unique from animals” (23). He further noted that “no society can do without a language. Man and language are inseparable and every man has the natural ability to use

language creatively and effectively in numerous ways. Language, therefore, is an essential tool for man's daily living. Its use depends on the user's experience, creativity and exposure to it.

Iuleha language is spoken in Owan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria (Augustine Ayeni 45). It is classified as the Proto-Edoid branch of the Niger-Congo language family. It is part of the North Central sub-group of Edoid languages with a population of speakers of above 100,000 plus (Ben Elugbe 89). English is a West Germanic language that belongs to the Indo-European language family, spoken in many countries of the world as the official language. English and Iuleha belong to two different language families; some of the plural formation processes in nominals are different, while some are similar. The area of differences would be of utmost importance in a contrastive study; Contrasting the first language (L1) with the second language (L2) would expose teachers to better teaching methods and materials to impact adequate knowledge in language learning.

Pronominal can be defined as lexical items; they are noun equivalents and belong to closed system items. The meaning of the word 'pronominal' comes from 'pro and nominal', which means the possibility of using pronouns instead of nouns (Randolph Quirk 30). They can get their meaning from the noun phrases for which they substitute. Pronominals rely on syntax and context for their interpretation (Rodman 20). A pronominal can function as a subject, object of a verb, and an object of a preposition. The pronoun must be equal to the noun phrase in terms of case subjective, objective, and possessive, personal and non-personal, number singular and plural, and finally in terms of gender feminine and masculine (Greenbaum Sidney 35).

English and Iuleha belong to two different language families; some of its plural formation processes in pronominal would probably be different while some might be similar. The area of differences would be of utmost importance in a contrastive study; this is because identifying the differences would provide insight into possible challenges, a second language learners (L2) in language learning situations with a view to enhancing better understanding. Here lies the need to investigate a contrastive analysis of pronominal formation processes in English and Iuleha Languages.

Review of Literature

There are studies carried out in contrastive analysis of different languages. Such as Augustine Ayeni in "Iuleha History and Language Studies", and Maria Pena carrying out "A Contrastive Analysis of Word Formation Processes in English and Spanish languages". Catherine Godwin on "The Sentence Structure of English and Igarra Languages", Ayo Babalola, and Akimade Akande on contrastive linguistics problems of Yoruba and English languages. Florence Obodeh on "The Morphological Structures in English and Ukwuani languages", Tunde Jija, on "Aspects of Tiv Pluralisation" etc., others are Robert Lado, Stephen Corder, Ben Elugbe, Francis Egbokhare and Sunday Tomori. In all of these studies, no attention has been given to the contrastive analysis of the pronominal processes in the Iuleha and English languages, which this study intends to cover. This study will act as a stepping stone to other areas of linguistic study in the Iuleha language which will serve as a reference point for school administrators, teachers and students as well as media practitioners. All these reviews revolve around the common notion that contrastive analysis is carried out to discover differences and similarities between two languages.

Methodology/ Data Collection Technique

The paper adopts the descriptive, expository and comparative methods of research. The methods above were supported by both the primary and secondary sources – the library and personal interviews. The study also adopts Halliday's Systemic Grammar as its Theoretical Framework. The "Systemic Grammar" views language as a network of systems, or interrelated set of options for making meaning. Ten (10) native respondents were interviewed in Iuleha, five (5) males and five (5) females. Among the respondents, 2 were between the ages of 65 and 80, 4 were between 45 and 60 and the other 4 respondents were between the ages of 20 and 40 respectively. This paper uses the marching method of contrastive analysis. Pronominal formation processes in both languages are fully described and compared side by side, and then, the similarities and differences are analysed.

Plural Pronominal Formation Processes in English

English pronominal can be classified into three, and they can be inflected to reflect their positions, function, gender and number in a given structure. These are personal pronoun, demonstrative pronoun, relative pronoun and non-personal, number singular and plural, and finally in terms of gender feminine and masculine (Leech & Randolph 355).

Furthermore, Sunday Tomori divided Personal pronouns in terms of singularity and plurality. The singular pronouns are I, he, she, and it and the plural pronouns are we, you, and they. They are also divided in terms of gender in which first and second person pronouns do not have gender distinctions. It means that the pronouns I, we, you are used whether the speaker is feminine or masculine whereas third person singular pronouns have gender distinctions. The pronoun he refers to male; the pronoun she refers to female; the pronoun it is used to indicate neither male nor female which is called neutral; and the pronoun they is used to indicate either male or female. Concerning case, the personal pronouns have three cases. The pronouns I, we, you, he, she, it, they are the pronouns of the subjective case as well as in the objective case, they are me, us, him, his, her, it, them, and you (Tomori 13). Another way of identifying a plural English Pronouns is into three grammatical persons: First person, second person and third person. Each person is divided into singular and plural. The singular pronouns are the following: "I", "he", "she", "you", "it", "me", "him", "his", "her", "hers", "your" and "its". The first five belong to subjective form while the remaining seven belong to the objective form. The following pronouns on the other hand belong to the plural pronouns: "We", "you", "they", "them", "us", "your", and their (theirs) – the first three are subjective while the rest are objective grammatically.

Table 1: Three Dimensions Applicable to Personal Pronouns in Plural Formation in English language.

Personal pronoun	Singularity	Plural
1 st Person	I	We
2 nd Person	You	You
3 rd Person	He/She/It	They

Demonstrative	This	These
	The/that	Those
Reflexive	Myself	Ourselves
	Yourself	Yourselves
	Him/herself	Themselves
Possessive	My	Ours
	Your	Yours
	Their	Theirs

Adopted from Randolph Quirk and Sidney Greenbaum (80)

It is worthy to also note that, Roberts wrote about the spoken *-s* plural marker long before most of other linguists – states how it can be realized in three different ways as outlined above. Roberts discusses the disagreement between the spoken *-s* as plural marker and the written *-s* or *-es* as plural marker. The personal pronouns must match their antecedents in terms of *case, person, number, and gender*.

Pronominal Formation Processes in Iuleha)

Iuleha Pronominals are formed through the dimensions applicable to persons. The first person *mè'mè* (I), or to the speaker and one or more others *má'mái* (we); Second person pronominal refers to the person(s) addressed *wèwè* (you) and third person *vbá'vbá* (them). In Iuleha, both *he/she* are unmarked for gender as in *nyòin singular* and *nyáin plural (he/she/ Them)*, irrespective of the gender. Demonstrative pronominals in Iuleha, constitute the same meaning: *Oná* (this), *Oni* (that) *énái* (these) or *éni* (those). Reflexive and Possessive Plural Pronominals as in *I'sèmè, Isá'vbá, Isá'mái, wewe, nyòin* and *nyáin*. These are better explained in the following:

Table 2: Three Dimensions Applicable to Personal Pronouns in Plural Formation in Iuleha.

Personal Pronoun	Singular (Root)	Gloss	Plural (Root)	Gloss (Meaning)
1 st Person	Mè̀mè̀	I	Ma'mai	We
2 nd Person	Wè̀wè̀	You	N'yáin	You
3 rd Person	Ny'òin	He/She/It	N'yáin/Vba'vbá	Them/They

(Adopted from Augustine Ayeni 12)

Iuleha language inflects for concord. Thus, the first person singular *Mémè* (I) and the first person plural *Má'mái* (we) generates a tonal inflection with a change in morphemic form to indicate the first person singular and the first person plural respectively as shown above.

Table 3: An illustration of the connectivity between first person pronoun and second/third person Pronominal.

Iuleha	Mémé	ògù'maé	Wèwè/ nyòin or ñyáín
Gloss	I	Said to	You as in Second person (singular), You as in Second person plural and them as in Third person plural

In the Iuleha: *Mé ògù'maé nyáin* (“I said to them”), the voiced bilabial nasal /m/ carries a high tone which is the first person singular *Mé* and *nyáin* which is the second/third person plural as the case may be. Thus, it can be said that the Iuleha first-person pronoun generates three forms. In the subjective position, it realizes the voiced bilabial nasal /m/ and the half-open front spread vowel /e/ *mé* (the Iuleha base form for I) if the subject only indicates the identity of reference, such as in the expression 'you' and 'I' (*wèwè lági mémè*). It also realizes *mémé* using pronominal reduplication, especially in contrastive clauses such as in the example above.

Table 4: An illustration of the connectivity between first person pronoun and second person plural

Iuleha	A'má	Mémé	Eyo	Wôr'eee
	[but]	[me]		
Gloss	<i>But</i>	<i>I</i> <i>First person singular (I)</i>	<i>Will do</i> <i>Future (will)</i>	<i>It</i> <i>Non human (it)</i>

Furthermore, the Iuleha first person pronoun *I*-subject undergoes inflection to indicate that what the verb signals is yet to be accomplished. In Iuleha, auxiliaries and modals are signalled by the noun, not by verbal element. (Ayeni 59) Thus, the voiced bilabial nasal sound /m/ (I) in *mémé* (“I said to you”) will become *mé* (“I” inflected to signal the auxiliary “will”) in *mé èyò'gù'maé wè* (“I will say to you”). Note also, that in “but I will do it,” the first person *I* in the English clause generates a reduplicated Iuleha pronoun *mè-mé* (*mè* (I). In addition, we also observe in the example, that the auxiliary and the main verb in English conflate into a single form of the *do* verb in Iuleha which conveys meaning that subsumes the objective *it* in English and thus does not need to be visibly indicated in Iuleha. Secondly, the voiced bilabial nasal sound /m/ and the *half open*

front spread vowel /a/ (*má*) is also the objective form of the first person plural pronoun in Iuleha. Thus, in *God said to us*, the objective *mái* would be used.

Table 5: Illustration of the connectivity between first person pronoun and third person plural

Iuleha	<u>Q</u> isèlobuá	<u>O</u> gù'ma'e	<i>mé'mè</i> first person
Gloss	God	Said to	(<i>him/her</i>) <i>ny'òin</i>

The Iuleha third person singular pronominal does not mark gender distinction like English does. Thus, both *he/she* are unmarked for gender. In reported speech, the pronoun in subjective position will be *nyòin* and the one in objective position will be *nyáin* (*he/she*), irrespective of the gender.

Table 6: Illustration of Iuleha third person pronominal plural formation.

Iuleha	N'yôin	<u>O</u> gù'ma'e	èliô	Gbèè
Gloss	He	Said to her	I will	Beat you
Iuleha	N'yôin	<u>O</u> gù'ma'e	èliô	chè'váe
Gloss	She	Said to him	I will	Come back

In Table 6, Iuleha language marks no distinction between the third person singular subjective pronominal (*he*) and the third person object pronominal (*she*); the voiced alveolar nasal /n/, voiced velar fricative /y/ and close mid back rounded vowel /o/ as in (*nyòin*) in singular and (*nyáin*) in plural does not mark either for gender. This creates a potential problem of translation in Iuleha. Thus, except where contextual cues provide strong relative identities between the genders in such situations as illustrated, the Iuleha translation would have to restate the antecedents as a means of disambiguation or seek other means to achieve clarity of reference.

Table 7: Iuleha illustration of Demonstrative Pronominals

Demonstrative	Iuleha	Gloss	Iuleha	Gloss
	<u>Ô</u> ná	This	éna	These

	<u>ò</u> ni	The/that	éni	Those
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(Personal Interview)

In Iuleha, demonstrative pronominals constitute the same meaning, the notion of referring to a particular person or thing. Examples are: Qná (this) or Oni (that) énáí (these) or éni (that). Below are other illustrations.

Oni (that) òni'òmqé ni oi mû éti

that man is not powerful

mái máti biô'lô'biá ní

we cannot do *that* work

E'nái (these) ènái èbe ôgho'mè

these are my books

Eni (those) óá mè'èni

those are my houses

háa ghé, èni olôì è'shán

look at *those* thieves are leaving

Table 8: Illustration of Reflexive and Possessive Plural Pronouns

	Iuleha	Gloss	Iuleha	Gloss
Reflexive	I'sèmè	Myself	I'sá'mái	Ourselves
	I'sè wè'wè	Yourself	I'sá'Vba'vba or nyôin	Yourselves
	Nyôin	Him/herself	Yáin	Themselves
Possessive	I'sèmè	My	Isá'mái	Ours
	I'sè	Your	Isè ee	Yours
	I'sè'yáin	Their	Isá'vbá	Theirs

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From the above examples in table 8, it is noted that both languages pronominal forms are gender neutral. However in English, there are a numbers of distinctions in the first person singular and plural. But there is no distinction in the second person singular and plural pronominal; both are (*you*). Iuleha have I'sèmè, Isá'vbá, Isá'mái, *wewe*, *nyòin* and *nyáin* respectively as the case may be.

Area of Differences and Similarities in Plural Nominals and Pronominals in English and Iuleha.

This paper shows that Iuleha pronominals do not make gender distinction while English does. Apart from nouns, plurals can be formed from pronominal as well, and it can be realized in different ways in Iuleha. Iuleha pronominal do not make gender distinction like English does. Thus, both *he* and *she* are unmarked for gender as in *nyôin/nyáin* respectively. Iuleha language also, does not observe the use of third person singular in pronominal processes. This is however observed in English language. The verb is determined by the status of the nominal (third person singular noun carries the alveolar fricatives 's' in the verb while the plural does not). It can therefore, be said that, the third person application is one of the differences between Iuleha and English plural formation processes. Both languages are similar in demonstrative and reflexive pronominal formation.

Conclusion

It is important to note that every language has its peculiarities and with certain similarities. The differences exhibited so far are enormous ,and it is capable of making the learning processes of English pronominals formation difficult. While the similarities will enhance learning. Therefore, the problems faced by learners of English in the Iuleha community are largely language interference, which resulted in errors in forming pronominals. The analysis shows that the major problem for learners of English in the Iuleha community is trying to use the first language acquisition L1 to form plural /pronominal in English. Learners of English in the Iuleha community must first, be able to distinguish these processes that are prevalent in both languages, accept the differences and commit them to memory before they can find the language easy to learn.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, this paper recommends that:

- (a) Since the differences in forming pronominals in both languages are enormous, the teacher should develop supplementary materials to aid in the teaching of English language; and
- (b) Other areas of English and Iuleha languages should also be compared to see the level of differences.

Works Cited

Ayeni, Augustine. *Iuleha History and Language Studies*. Edo: Head Mark Publishers, 2019.

- Print.
- Acheoah Emike,. “A Contrastive of English and Afemai Morphology”. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities* 1 (2013): 29-35. Print.
- Akande, Akimade. "Acquisition of English Language". *Nordic Journal of African Studies*
- Al-Hassan, Bello Reduplication in Chadic Languages. New York: Peter Lang. 2003.Print.
- ___.“Does Hausa Really Have Infixation?” Unpublished Seminar Paper Presented at the Department of Nigerian and African Languages, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria: 2006. Print.
- Aliyu, Salihu “Morphological Processes of Gbari and English: A Contrastive Study.” An Unpublished M. A. Seminar Paper Presented at the Department of English and Literary Studies, Faculty of Arts , Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. 2014. Print.
- Andrew, Christiana, “A Comparative Analysis of English and Igala Morphological Processes.” An Unpublished M. A. Thesis Submitted to the Department of English and Literary Studies, Faculty of Arts, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. 2006. Print.
- Aremo, Bolaji. “Nouns Illustrating Adjective –Noun Conversion in English”. *Asian EFL M.A Dissertation, ABU, Department of English*, 2005. Print.
- Azar, Betty Schramper *Understanding and Using English Grammar*. London: Longman. 2003. Print.
- Azar, Betty, Barbara, Frank & Shelly, Hugh. *Understanding and Using English Grammar* (3rd ed.). London: Longman. 2018. Print.
- Berk, Laura. *English Syntax*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 1999. Print.
- Betti, Mike. Jones Jokes in Iraq: A Study of Coherence and Cohesion. *Journal of the College of Education—University of Wassit*, 1(1), 399–411. 2017. Print.
- Booij, Geert. *The Grammar of Words: An Introduction to Linguistic Morphology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 2005. Print.
- Corder, Stephen. *Introducing Applied Linguistic*. Oxford: University Press, 2003. Print.
- Chomsky, Noam. *New Horizons in the Study of Language and Mind*. New York: The New Press, 2007. Print.
- Crystal, David. *Linguistics*. London: Penguin, 1999. Print
- Dooga, Jerome Terpase. “A Contrastive Analysis of the Pronoun in English and Tiv”. *Jos Journal of Theatre, Arts and Film* (Vol. 1: No. 1) January, 2019. 133-142 Print.
- Elugbe, Ben. *Comparative Edoid Phonology and Lexicon*. Delta Series Portharcort: University

- of Port Harcourt Press, 1989. Print.
- Egbokhare, Francis “Nasality in Emai”. *Afrika Und Uberse*. Hamburg: University of Hamburg. 1990. Print.
- -. “Sounds of Meaning”. An Inaugural Lecture Series of the University of Ibadan. University Press, 2011. Print.
- Quirk, Randolph, Sidney Greenbaum, Geoffrey Leech, Jan Svartvik. *A Grammar of Contemporary English*. London: Longman, 1972. Print.
- Smith, Rebecca. “The Noun Class System of U.MA”. A West Kainji Language in Nigeria. M.A. Thesis University of North Dakoto. 2007. Print.
- Greenbaum, S., Leech, G., & Svartvik, J. *A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*. England: London. 2015. Print.
- Rodman, Rich. & Hyams, Newton. *An Introduction to Language*. Belmont: Thomson Wadsworth. 2007. Print.
- Tomori, Sunday. *An introduction to the Morphology of Present Day English*. Heinemann Educational Books Ltd. Halley Court Jordan Hill Oxford. 2016. Print.